

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF LED TELEVISION TRAINER

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Development and Evaluation of LED Television Trainer

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Abstract

The electronics industry faces challenges such as insufficient instructional materials and limited access to relevant teaching tools, demonstrations, and hands-on lab exercises, all of which are crucial for enhancing electronics education for both educators and students. The increasing enrollment of electronics students and rapid technological advancements prompted the researcher to develop concrete and tangible devices for electronics education. This study aimed to develop and evaluate an LED Television Trainer as a supplemental teaching aid in electronics technology. The trainer was designed and developed using the developmental research method and assessed through a descriptive-evaluative approach. Sixty participants, comprising students, TLE teachers, and technicians from various electronics shops and service centers, evaluated the trainer's design and construction, durability, safety, functionality, and instructional applicability through surveys and experiments. The evaluation results demonstrated high acceptability across all criteria, with respondents consistently providing positive feedback that highlighted the trainer's effectiveness and efficiency in facilitating the learning and practical application of LED television technology. This strong endorsement underscores the trainer's potential to enhance educational outcomes, addressing the challenges of insufficient instructional materials and limited access to electronic tools. The study concludes that the LED Television Trainer prototype exemplifies how such innovations can positively transform learning experiences, equipping students with practical skills and knowledge that extend beyond the classroom to meet industry demands.

Keywords: *LED television trainer, electronics education, instructional materials, developmental research, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE)*

Introduction

The rapidly evolving technological landscape necessitates the continuous development of innovative teaching resources to provide students with the knowledge and skills required for the modern workforce. In the field of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), particularly in electronics, the challenge of delivering quality education is often exacerbated by the lack of adequate instructional materials. This gap not only impedes the learning process but also affects students' ability to master complex concepts and practical skills, which are critical for their future careers (Smith & Mistry, 2016; Johnson & Clayton, 2018).

Traditional instructional materials, while foundational, often fall short in preparing students for the complexities of modern electronic systems. Research has shown that hands-on learning tools, such as trainer kits and simulation models, significantly enhance students' comprehension and retention of technical knowledge (Brown & Green, 2019; Reigeluth, 2020). These tools provide a more interactive and engaging learning experience, which is crucial in fostering a deeper understanding of electronic circuits and components (Kirkwood & Price, 2014; Schunk, 2016).

The introduction of LED televisions as a common household technology presents an opportunity to innovate within the educational sector. LED TVs, with their advanced features and widespread usage, serve as an ideal platform for developing instructional trainers that can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application (Anderson & Anderson, 2019; Kumar & Mishra, 2021). The development of an LED Television Trainer aligns with the current trend of integrating real-world technologies into educational settings, thereby making learning more relevant and effective (Johnson et al., 2019).

In the context of the K–12 Program implemented by the Department of Education in the Philippines, there is a growing emphasis on equipping students with 21st-century skills that are globally competitive (DepEd, 2020). The curriculum for TLE, particularly in electronics, includes competencies in servicing consumer electronic products, where mastery is essential for students' future careers as technicians or engineers (TESDA, 2018). However, the effectiveness of this curriculum is often limited by the availability and quality of instructional materials (Marsh & Willis, 2021; Cohen & Ball, 2019).

The LED Television Trainer developed in this study aims to address these challenges by providing a hands-on learning tool that simulates real-world electronics scenarios. This trainer is designed to enhance students' practical skills and cognitive understanding by allowing them to engage directly with the components and functions of an LED TV (Cobb et al., 2018; Sawyer, 2014). Incorporating this trainer into the TLE curriculum allows educators to create a more dynamic and immersive learning environment that promotes active learning and skill retention (Laurillard, 2012; Bandura, 2019).

This study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of the LED Television Trainer in improving students' competencies in electronics education. It also aims to provide recommendations for the broader implementation of such trainers in educational institutions, thereby enhancing the quality of TLE instruction and better-preparing students for future technological challenges (Mayer, 2020; Jonassen, 2017).

Research Questions

This research aimed to design, develop, and evaluate the LED Television Trainer. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the steps in designing and developing the proposed LED Television Trainer?
2. What are the technical specifications of the proposed LED Television Trainer?
3. What experiments can be performed using the LED Television Trainer?
4. What is the level of acceptability of the proposed LED Television Trainer in terms of:
 - 4.1. design and construction;
 - 4.2. functionality;
 - 4.3. durability;
 - 4.4. safety; and
 - 4.5. instructional capability?
5. What is the general level of acceptability of the LED TV Trainer as evaluated by the respondents:
 - 5.1. TLE teachers/instructors,
 - 5.2. electronics technicians/experts; and
 - 5.3. students?
6. Is there a significant difference in the evaluation of the respondents in the level of acceptability in terms of:
 - 6.1. design and construction;
 - 6.2. functionality;
 - 6.3. durability;
 - 6.4. safety; and
 - 6.5. instructional capability?

Literature Review

The ultimate goal of the study is the development and evaluation of an LED Television Trainer to enhance the teaching of electronics for both high school and college students majoring in Electronics. The trainer is an effective instructional material to let students bridge theory and practice in Electronics Education.

The Importance of Instructional Materials in Education

Instructional materials are crucial in enhancing the quality of education by providing learners with the necessary tools to acquire knowledge and develop skills (Smith & Mistry, 2016). These materials help bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical applications, making learning more effective and engaging (Brown & Green, 2019). In the context of electronics education, where students must grasp complex technical concepts, the role of instructional materials becomes even more critical (Cohen & Ball, 2019).

Challenges in Electronics Education

Electronics education faces significant challenges, particularly in resource-limited environments. The lack of adequate instructional materials often hampers the teaching and learning process, leading to gaps in students' understanding and retention of critical concepts (Johnson & Clayton, 2018). The need for practical, hands-on experience is paramount in electronics education, yet many schools struggle to provide the necessary tools and equipment due to budget constraints or outdated resources (Cobb et al., 2018; Marsh & Willis, 2021).

Advancements in Educational Technology

The rapid advancement of technology has introduced new opportunities for developing innovative instructional materials that enhance learning. Educational technology has shifted towards more interactive and immersive tools, such as simulation models and trainer kits, which provide students with a more engaging and effective learning experience (Kirkwood & Price, 2014; Reigeluth, 2020). These advancements have proven particularly beneficial in technical education, where hands-on practice is essential (Anderson & Anderson, 2019).

The Role of Trainer Tools in Technical Education

According to Johnson et al. (2019), trainer kits or tools have become increasingly popular in technical education for their ability to simulate real-world scenarios in a controlled environment. These kits allow students to experiment with electronic circuits and components, thereby improving their practical skills and understanding of theoretical concepts (Sawyer, 2014). The development of trainer kits tailored to specific technologies, such as LED televisions, represents a significant advancement in instructional design, providing students with relevant and up-to-date learning experiences (Mayer, 2020; Jonassen, 2017).

LED Television Technology in Education

LED televisions, with their advanced features and widespread use, offer a unique opportunity for integration into educational settings

(Kumar & Mishra, 2021). As a modern electronic device, LED TVs present complex systems that can be deconstructed and studied in detail, making them an ideal focus for educational trainer kits (Laurillard, 2012). The incorporation of LED TV technology into the TLE curriculum aligns with current trends in educational technology and provides students with practical skills that are directly applicable to the real world (Bandura, 2019).

Impact of Hands-On Learning on Student Outcomes

Numerous studies have shown that hands-on learning significantly improves student outcomes by nurturing deeper engagement and better retention of knowledge (Schunk, 2016; Smith et al., 2018). When students can interact directly with the materials they are learning about, they are more likely to understand and remember complex concepts (Cobb et al., 2018). This approach is particularly effective in technical education, where the practical application of knowledge is key to student success (Kirkwood & Price, 2014).

Curriculum Development and Instructional Materials

The development of effective instructional materials is closely tied to curriculum design. A well-designed curriculum integrates these materials in a way that enhances learning and supports the achievement of educational objectives (Cohen & Ball, 2019). The K-12 program in the Philippines, which emphasizes 21st-century skills and global competitiveness, highlights the importance of innovative instructional materials in achieving these goals (DepEd, 2020). The integration of LED Television Trainers into the TLE curriculum represents a forward-thinking approach to addressing the challenges of electronics education (TESDA, 2018).

Evaluation of Instructional Tools

The evaluation of instructional tools, such as trainer kits, is essential to ensure their effectiveness in enhancing student learning (Jonassen, 2017). Effective evaluation involves assessing not only the tools' ability to convey theoretical knowledge but also their impact on students' practical skills and overall learning outcomes (Mayer, 2020). Studies have shown that well-designed instructional tools can significantly improve both cognitive and practical competencies in students (Anderson & Anderson, 2019; Schunk, 2016).

Recommendations for Future Research and Implementation

Based on the existing literature, future research needs to focus on further developing and refining instructional materials that cater to the specific needs of technical education (Reigeluth, 2020). The broader implementation of tools like the LED Television Trainer could greatly enhance the quality of electronics education, particularly in resource-limited settings (Johnson & Clayton, 2018). Moreover, ongoing evaluation and adaptation of these tools are crucial to ensure they remain relevant and effective in an ever-changing technological landscape (Sawyer, 2014; Marsh & Willis, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The development of the 32-inch L.E.D. Television Trainer utilized a developmental and descriptive-evaluative research method. The identified processes were thoroughly followed for the technical design, project construction, testing, and evaluation of the trainer's effectiveness and performance. Furthermore, modifications were made to the trainer's technical features following documented findings and results.

Respondents

The respondents of this study used three groups, which consist of twenty (20) participants per group, namely, the TLE teachers from junior and senior high schools within the Schools Division Office of Isabela (SDO-Isabela) and electronics instructors from Isabela State University- Angadanan Campus, electronics technicians and experts from different shops and service centers in the Province of Isabela, and the grade 10 electronics students from Fugaru Integrated School, Angadanan West District, Fugaru Angadanan, Isabela.

Instrument

The instrument used to evaluate the trainer's effectiveness was adopted from Bartolome's (2020) study titled "Development and Acceptability of Industrial Motor Control Trainer." The respondents evaluated the trainer's design and construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. The collected data was analyzed and treated using the five-point Likert scale.

Procedure

All the data gathered from the performance of the trainer was observed and recorded through a sequence of tests to get the necessary technical specifications and details to enhance the capabilities and features of the trainer.

Moreover, the trainer was evaluated by the three respondent groups, which included TLE teachers, electronics technicians, and grade 10 electronics students of Fugaru Integrated School. Permission from the school heads was requested for the participation of the respondents to answer the given questionnaire right after the presentation and demonstration on how the L.E.D. Television Trainer works.

Data Analysis

All the data collected via the questionnaire were processed using descriptive statistics to interpret the trainer's performance.

The Weighted Mean was applied to determine the trainer's level of acceptability in terms of design and construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability.

An Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there was a significant difference in the respondents' evaluations of the trainer's acceptability.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, the researcher upheld ethical standards by ensuring integrity, transparency, and respect for participants' rights. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before starting the study. Moreover, the researcher ensured that measures were taken to safeguard the participants' welfare. No conflicts of interest were present, and strict avoidance of plagiarism was maintained. The interpretation of findings remained unbiased, and the results were utilized solely for the study.

Results and Discussion

Steps in Designing and Developing the LED Television Trainer

The construction of the LED Television Trainer involved several systematic steps. Initially, the identification, preparation, and acquisition of supplies and materials for the project were completed. The next step involved taking measurements and cutting the ½ inch marine plywood, followed by assembling the casing of the trainer. Common faults and voltage test points were then identified. The LED TV, main board, speakers, control panel keys, voltage test points, fault switches, and other components were mounted onto the casing. Holes were drilled for mounting the terminal binding posts for the voltage test points and fault switches. Measuring instruments, including analog and digital multi-testers and an LED backlight strip tester, were then mounted. Wires were soldered and connected to the different sections and terminals, after which the various parts and sections of the trainer were labeled with stickers. The fault switches and voltage test point connections were then inspected and tested. Finally, the trainer's performance was tested, measured voltages were recorded, and any necessary revisions for improvements were made.

The Designed and Developed LED Television Trainer

A successful output is the product of following the step-by-step process of designing and developing the LED TV trainer. The picture shown is the actual appearance of the project.

Figure 1. Front view of the completed LED Television Trainer

Technical Specifications of the LED Television Trainer

The technical specifications of the project include the performance of voltage test points and the details of components used in the construction of the trainer.

Table 1. Technical Specifications on Voltage Test Points of the Trainer

Legend/Codes	Test Points	Standard Voltage on LED TV	Measured Voltage using an Analog Multimeter	Measured Voltage using a Digital Multimeter
1A	Primary Filter Capacitor	125-300 VDC	240V	264.2V
1B	Secondary Filter Capacitor	12V VDC	11V	12.10V
2B	Regulator IC (6pins)	5V	5V	5.13V
3B	Regulator IC (1118)	1.8V	1.6V	1.81V
4B	Secondary Filter Capacitor	12V	11V	12.10V
5B	Secondary Filter Capacitor	12V	11V	11.81V

6B	Backlight Inverter Supply	58V	55V	58.02V
7B	Memory IC Supply	3.3V	3.2V	3.29V
8B	Regulator IC (5pins)	1.2V	1V	1.21V
9B	IR & keys board	5V	5V	5.12V
10B	USB Supply	5V	5V	5.12V
11B	Backlight Inverter Supply	24V	24V	24.79V
1C	Top Board Supply	12V	11V	11.67V
	VCC+			
2C	VGH	20-30V	27V	27.83V
3C	VAA	15V	14V	15.32V
4C	VCM	5V	5.2V	5.41V
5C	VDD	3.3V	3V	3.01V
6C	VGL	-7.8V	-7.8V	-7.96V
7C	HVAA	6V	6.8V	6.87V
8C	VCM2	9V	9.2V	9.42V

Table 1 displays the normal voltages that can be measured in the test points of the trainer. The legend and letter codes have corresponding standard voltages, which are directly connected to the target test points and can be measured using analog and digital multimeters. The table also shows the LCD panel circuit board voltages, which are letter-coded from 1C to 8C. Panel voltages include VCC, which means common collector voltage; VGH, for voltage gate high; VAA, for analog operating voltage; VCM, for common-mode voltage; VDD, for digital operating voltage; VGL, for voltage gate low; and HVAA, also known as AVDD, stands for analog power supply voltage.

Table 2. *Technical Specifications Table of the LED Television Trainer*
Power Requirements: 220V-240V AC/50-Hz

	Device	Quantity	Voltage Rating	Current Rating
1.	32" LED TV (Astron)	1	100VAC-240VAC	0.14A
2.	Toggle Switch	14	125VAC	6A
3.	Banana Plug 4mm	54	30V	15A
4.	Banana Socket 4mm	48	30V	15A
5.	Terminal Binding Post	4	250V	15A
6.	Banana Socket 2mm	24	30V	15A
7.	12 VDC Unregulated Power Supply	1 unit	12 VDC	1A
8.	LED Backlight Strip	2	3 VDC	100mA
9.	SEESAW Switch	1	250VAC	15A
10.	Fuse	1	250VAC	1A

Table 3. *Test Instruments Technical Specifications Table*

	Device	Quantity	Brand	Model Number
1.	Analog Multimeter	1	Sanwa	YX360TRF
2.	Digital Multimeter	1	ZOTEK	ZT102
3.	LED Backlight Strip Tester	1	SFDER	SFD-290

The table presents the technical specifications of the electronic components, devices, and test instruments used in the trainer.

Experiments and Activities that can be performed using the LED Television Trainer

Table 4. *Experiments and Activities performed using the LED Television Trainer*

Topics	Activities
Chapter 1. Introduction	
1. History of the Television Receiver	Written Assessment Knowing the history of Television Receiver
2. Differences between LCD and LED TV	Written Assessment (Identification)
3. Common Parts of an LED TV	Identifying common parts of the LED TV.
	Written Assessment
4. LED TV Trainer Activity Board and Parts Familiarization	Identifying and labeling the parts of the LED TV Trainer Activity Board
5. Diagram Connections	Identification Performance Task: Wiring/connecting the circuits of the LED TV Trainer
Chapter 2. Voltage Testing	
1. Primary (Hot) Section	Measuring actual voltage using analog and digital multimeters.

2. Secondary (Cold) Section	Measuring actual voltage using analog and digital multimeters.
3. LCD Panel Board Section	Measuring actual voltage using analog and digital multimeters.
Chapter 3. Simulation Of Common Faults And Troubles	
Power Troubles	
No Power	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Intermittent Power	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Standby	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
IR & Keys Failure	
Control keys are not working	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Remote Control is not working	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
No Channel/No Signal	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
USB is not working	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Sound Troubles	
No Sound (Left)	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
No Sound (Right)	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
No Sound (A/V mode)	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Panel/Display Troubles	
No Picture but good backlight	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
No Picture/no display	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
Dim Picture	Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting
No Video (A/V Mode)	Wiring LED Backlight Ports Activating Fault Switches Actual Voltage Testing Troubleshooting

The table above presents the experiments and activities that can be performed using the LED TV Trainer. From the first column, there are three chapters wherein it is based on the crafted user or activity manual. The lessons derived from Chapter 1 give the students a fundamental understanding of the development of television receivers.

The exercises in Chapters 2 and 3 are made to provide students with practical experience and the opportunity to carry out specific experiments related to voltage testing, diagnosing, and repairing LED TVs.

Furthermore, actual and common LED TV faults and troubles are integrated into the trainer coupled with voltage testing, to allow students to experience the real-life scenario of repairing television receivers.

Table 5. *Details on Experiments of Simulated Faults and Troubles of the Trainer*

Switch Code	Name of Fault and Trouble	Symptom/s		Block/Section/Part	Possible Defect/s	Corrective Measures
		Audio	Video			
A	No Power	No Sound	No Display	Power Supply	-Open AC Cord -Loose Connections -Open Switch -Open Fuse -Shorted Rectifier Diodes -Corroded terminal of the main filter capacitor	-Replace the AC cord if necessary. -Resolder the loose or cold solder. -Replace faulty switch. -Replace defective fuse. -Replace defective diodes. -Replace defective capacitor.
B	Standby	No Sound	No Display	Power Supply	-Loose connections. -Open the circuit on the secondary supply section. -No supply voltage in the memory IC.	-Resolder terminals in the LVPS section. -Reconnect the open circuit using a jumper wire. -Reconnect open voltage tracks if there are any. -Replace open fusible resistors.
C	Intermittent Power	On & off sound	On & off display	Power Supply	-Loose connections. -Shorted tact switches	-Resolder terminals in the LVPS section. -Replace shorted tact switches.
D	The remote control is not working	Normal	Normal	Mainboard	-Broken circuit (remote controller) -Low or drained battery. -Open circuit on IR keys board.	-Connect any broken circuit of the remote controller. -Replace old batteries. -Reconnect open circuits.
E	Control keys are not working	Normal	Normal	Infrared & keys board	-Open tact switches -Loose connections. -Open circuit	-Clean the contacts of the switch or replace them with new ones. -Resolder terminals and axial leads of the tact switches. -Replace all tact switches if necessary.
F	USB is not working	Normal	Normal	Mainboard	-Cold solder -Open circuit -Corrupted Files on flash drives	-Resolder USB terminals in the mainboard. -Reconnect open circuits using a soldering iron. -Replace the USB flash drive.
G	No sound (Left)	No Sound	Normal	Audio/Mainboard	-Open/ burnt speaker -Cold solder -Audio amplifier	-Replace defective speaker. -Resolder speaker terminals. -Replace defective IC.
H	No signal/ No channel	Normal	No picture	Tuner/Mainboard	-Loose connections. -Open Circuit -Antenna	-Resolder the loose terminals. -Reconnect the detected open circuit. -Arrange and secure the antenna's placement.
I	No display/No picture	Normal	No display/ no picture	LED Backlight Strip/Mainboard	-Loose connections. -LED Backlights -LED Backlight Driver -T-con/Top Board	-Resolder loose contacts. -Replace any defective parts in the backlight driver circuit. -Replace defective fuse.
J	No picture but good backlight	Normal	No display	Mainboard/Top board	-LED Backlights -Loose contacts -LED Backlight Driver	-Replace burnt lamp beads or the whole backlight strip. -Resolder loose contacts. -Replace faulty spare parts on the backlight driver circuit.
K	Dim picture	Normal	Dim display/ picture	LED Backlight Strip	-LED Backlights	- Replace burnt lamp beads or the whole backlight strip.
L	No video (AV mode)	No Sound	No display	Mainboard	-RCA cord -Audio/Video (AV) jack	-Replace RCA -Clean or replace RCA jacks.
M	No sound (TV & AV mode)	No Sound	Normal	Audio/Mainboard	-Open/ burnt speaker -Cold solder	-Replace defective speaker. -Resolder speaker terminals.
N	No Sound (Right)	No Sound	Normal	Audio/Mainboard	-Open/ burnt speaker -Cold solder	-Replace defective speaker. -Resolder speaker terminals.

Table 5 displays the technical information needed to understand the operation of the trainer. The switch codes reveal the actual faults and troubles that the trainer can simulate which serves as a troubleshooting guide for electronics students. The table also presents the

symptoms, specific blocks, sections, and parts of the affected circuit on where to focus in solving LED TV problems. In the other column, the possible defects and corrective measures to fix each stated fault and trouble are provided.

Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer

Table 6. *Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in Terms of Design and Construction*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The overall look of the design and construction of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.88	0.3237	Very Good
2. The components and parts of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.73	0.4459	Very Good
3. The uniqueness of the design and construction of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.70	0.4621	Very Good
4. The flexibility of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.55	0.5017	Very Good
5. The electrical components of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.70	0.4621	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.71	0.2740	Very Good

The table presents the results of an evaluation regarding the acceptability of a proposed 32-inch LED Television Trainer in terms of its design and construction.

Mean Scores and Standard Deviations

For the Overall Look of the Design and Construction of the LED TV Trainer, the mean –is 4.88 with a standard deviation of 0.3237, described as “Very Good” by the respondents. In terms of its Flexibility, it has a mean of 4.55 with a standard deviation of 0.5017 described also as “Very Good” by the respondents.

The mean scores across all indicators are consistently high, ranging from 4.55 to 4.88, indicating a strong level of acceptability for the proposed LED Television Trainer in terms of its design and construction. Also, the standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from 0.2740 to 0.5017), suggesting that respondents' opinions were generally consistent across the different aspects evaluated.

Findings suggest that the "Very Good" ratings across the board indicate that the LED Television Trainer meets or exceeds expectations in terms of design and construction.

The feedback suggests that stakeholders find the design appealing, the components satisfactory, and the overall concept unique and flexible enough for its intended purpose. Further, the table reflects a positive reception of the proposed LED Television Trainer's design and construction, with "Very Good" ratings across all evaluated indicators, indicating strong acceptability among the evaluators.

Table 7. *Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in Terms of Functionality*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The design of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer is effective for instructional purposes.	4.88	0.3237	Very Functional
2. The 32-inch LED TV Trainer can perform many other related activities and operations for students to use properly.	4.68	0.4691	Very Functional
3. The overall performance of the 32-inch LED TV trainer in all its intended uses for different activities.	4.70	0.4621	Very Functional
4. The developed 32-inch LED TV Trainer serves its purpose efficiently and effectively.	4.70	0.4621	Very Functional
5. The design of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer allows for the activities to proceed from simple to complex.	4.68	0.4691	Very Functional
6. The 32-inch LED TV Trainer is made up of real electronic components used in the operation, testing, and troubleshooting procedures.	4.83	0.3758	Very Functional
7. The student's training progress is monitored through a modularized approach ensuring mastery and clarity of training in electronics.	4.53	0.5357	Very Functional
Overall Mean	4.72	0.2112	Very Functional

The table shows an evaluation of the acceptability of a proposed 32-inch LED Television Trainer based on its functionality.

For the High Functionality of the LED TV Trainer, it was rated with mean scores for functionality are consistently high, ranging from 4.53 to 4.88, indicating a strong perception of functionality across different aspects of the LED Television Trainer. In addition, the standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from 0.2112 to 0.5357), suggesting that there is general agreement among respondents regarding the functionality of the trainer.

The trainer is highly rated for its effectiveness in instructional purposes with a mean score of 4.88. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator, monitoring training progress through a modularized approach (mean = 4.53), could potentially benefit from further refinement or clarity in how training progress is tracked and ensured.

The consistently high ratings underpin a strong acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in terms of functionality. It suggests that the trainer meets expectations in facilitating learning through practical application and effective performance of electronic operations.

In conclusion, data demonstrates that the proposed LED Television Trainer is highly regarded for its functionality across various dimensions, with "Very Functional" ratings indicating strong overall acceptability among evaluators.

Table 8. *Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in Terms of Durability*

Indicator	Mean	Sd	Description
1. The various materials used in making the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.72	0.4544	Very Durable
2. The frame assembly of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.77	0.4646	Very Durable
3. The materials used in the 32-inch LED TV Trainer can be used for a longer period.	4.60	0.4940	Very Durable
4. The various materials used in making the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.58	0.5302	Very Durable
5. The different modules of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.68	0.4691	Very Durable
Overall Mean	4.67	0.2751	Very Durable

The table provides an assessment of the acceptability of a proposed 32-inch LED Television Trainer in terms of its durability.

As presented in the table, the mean scores across all indicators are consistently high, ranging from 4.58 to 4.77, indicating a strong perception of durability for different aspects of the LED Television Trainer. Also, the standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from 0.2751 to 0.5302), suggesting that there is general agreement among respondents regarding the durability of the trainer.

As gleaned in the table, the respondents find the materials used in the trainer (including frame assembly and various components) to be very durable, with mean scores ranging from 4.58 to 4.77. Likewise, the perception of the longevity of materials is also high (mean = 4.60 to 4.68), indicating confidence in the trainer's ability to withstand prolonged use.

The consistently high ratings suggest that the LED Television Trainer is perceived as durable across its construction and components. This durability is crucial for educational and training purposes, ensuring that the trainer can withstand repeated use in learning environments without significant wear or degradation.

Findings indicate that the proposed LED Television Trainer is highly regarded for its durability, with "Very Durable" ratings across all evaluated indicators and this is evident with the overall mean score of 4.67. This strong acceptability underscores the trainer's suitability for long-term use in educational settings.

Table 9. *Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in Terms of Safety*

Indicator	Mean	Sd	Description
1. The developed 32-inch LED TV Trainer is safe to use and user-friendly.	4.85	0.3601	Very Safe
2. The safety condition of the parts and components of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.77	0.4265	Very Safe
3. The installed electrical/electronic components of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.63	0.4860	Very Safe
4. The various materials used in making the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.65	0.5150	Very Safe
5. The different modules of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer.	4.55	0.5017	Very Safe
Overall Mean	4.69	0.2536	Very Safe

The table exhibits an evaluation of the proposed 32-inch LED Television Trainer in terms of its safety.

As presented in the table, the mean scores for safety are consistently high, ranging from 4.55 to 4.85, indicating a strong perception of safety across different aspects of the LED Television Trainer. In addition, the standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from 0.2536 to 0.5150), suggesting general agreement among respondents regarding the safety of the trainer.

One of the strengths of the LED Trainer is its User-Friendliness: The trainer is highly rated for being safe to use and user-friendly with the highest mean score of 4.85, indicating good design consideration for user safety and was considered "Very Safe" to use. Additionally, the materials used and different modules of the trainer also scored well in terms of safety with a mean score of 4.55.

The high ratings suggest that the LED Television Trainer meets or exceeds safety expectations across its design, components, materials, and modules. Safety is crucial in educational settings, ensuring that students can use the trainer without risks or hazards, which this evaluation supports.

In conclusion, results demonstrate that the proposed LED Television Trainer is highly regarded for its safety, with "Very Safe" ratings across all evaluated indicators. This is supported by its overall mean of 4.69 which described that the trainer is "Very Safe" to use. This strong acceptability underscores the trainer's suitability for use in educational environments where safety is paramount.

Table 10. *Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer in Terms of Instructional Applicability*

Indicator	Mean	Sd	Description
1. The 32-inch LED TV Trainer is effective for instructional and workshop use.	4.95	0.2198	Very Applicable
2. The 32-inch LED TV Trainer can be used for Electronics/TLE subjects and laboratories.	4.93	0.2515	Very Applicable
3. The operation and manipulation of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer are according to the needed performance for each designed activity.	4.95	0.2198	Very Applicable
4. The use of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer improves the teaching-learning process.	4.85	0.3601	Very Applicable
5. The operation and manipulation of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer are according to the needed action for each activity.	4.72	0.4544	Very Applicable
Overall Mean	4.88	0.1774	Very Applicable

The table evaluates the acceptability of the proposed 32-inch LED Television Trainer in terms of its instructional applicability.

Data show that the respondents view the trainer as “Very Applicable” based on its overall mean of 4.88. This indicates a very high level of agreement among respondents that the LED Television Trainer is highly applicable for instructional purposes.

The mean scores for instructional applicability are consistently high, ranging from 4.72 to 4.95, indicating a strong perception of the trainer's effectiveness and suitability across various educational contexts. The standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from 0.1774 to 0.4544), suggesting strong agreement among respondents regarding the applicability of the trainer.

The trainer is highly rated for its effectiveness in instructional and workshop settings and on its operation and manipulation, both having a mean score of 4.95 and evaluated by the respondents as “Very Applicable. Likewise, the operation and manipulation of the 32-inch LED TV Trainer according to the needed action for each activity were rated with a mean of 4.72 and evaluated by the respondents as “Very Applicable”.

The high ratings underscore the trainer's strong suitability and effectiveness for enhancing educational practices in electronics and related subjects. Its adaptability across different activities and its perceived enhancement of the teaching-learning process are significant strengths highlighted in this evaluation.

Findings demonstrate that the proposed LED Television Trainer is highly regarded for its instructional applicability, with "Very Applicable" ratings across all evaluated indicators. This high level of acceptability suggests that the trainer effectively supports educational goals and enhances learning experiences in electronics and related fields.

General Level of Acceptability

Table 11. General Level of Acceptability of the LED TV Trainer as Evaluated by the Respondents

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Description</i>
TLE Teachers/Instructors	Design and Construction	4.88	0.1765	Very Good
	Functionality	4.88	0.1624	Very Functional
	Durability	4.81	0.2634	Very Durable
	Safety	4.84	0.2010	Very Safe
	Instructional Applicability	4.97	0.0733	Very Applicable
Overall Mean		4.88		Very Acceptable
Electronics Technicians/Experts	Design and Construction	4.61	0.3144	Very Good
	Functionality	4.61	0.2129	Very Functional
	Durability	4.54	0.2683	Very Durable
	Safety	4.61	0.2292	Very Safe
	Instructional Applicability	4.86	0.2062	Very Applicable
Overall Mean		4.65		Very Acceptable
Students	Design and Construction	4.65	0.2417	Very Good
	Functionality	4.66	0.1565	Very Functional
	Durability	4.66	0.2349	Very Durable
	Safety	4.62	0.2668	Very Safe
	Instructional Applicability	4.81	0.1889	Very Applicable
Overall Mean		4.68		Very Acceptable

The table provides a breakdown of the general level of acceptability of the LED TV Trainer as evaluated by TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education) Teachers/Instructors

A mean score of 4.88 suggests that the LED TV Trainer is highly regarded across all evaluated aspects or by all respondent groups. This score typically indicates a high level of satisfaction or acceptability among those who have evaluated the trainer. This means that TLE Teachers/Instructors find the LED TV Trainer highly acceptable across all evaluated criteria, with particularly strong endorsements for its instructional applicability, functionality, and safety. These ratings affirm the trainer's suitability for educational use and suggest it meets or exceeds expectations in supporting teaching and learning objectives effectively.

Also, the overall mean across all criteria is 4.65, which is described as "Very Acceptable." This indicates a strong general level of acceptability among Electronics Technicians/Experts for the LED TV Trainer. Further, Electronics Technicians/Experts find the LED TV Trainer highly acceptable across all evaluated criteria, with strong endorsements for its functionality, safety, and instructional applicability. These ratings affirm the trainer's suitability for professional use and its effectiveness in supporting skill development and educational objectives in electronics.

In addition, for the students, the overall mean across all criteria is 4.68, which is described as "Very Acceptable." This indicates a strong general level of acceptability among Students for the LED TV Trainer. Hence, the students find the LED TV Trainer highly acceptable across all evaluated criteria, indicating their positive perceptions of its design, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. These ratings affirm the trainer's effectiveness in supporting learning outcomes and its suitability for use in

educational environments.

Comparison in the LED Television Trainer's Level of Acceptability as Evaluated by Respondents

Table 12. Comparison in the Evaluation of the Respondents in the Level of Acceptability of the LED Television Trainer

Criteria	F-Value	ρ -Value	Decision	Remarks
Design and Construction	6.7615	0.0023	Reject H0	Significant
Functionality	12.5499	0.0000	Reject H0	Significant
Durability	5.5870	0.0061	Reject H0	Significant
Safety	6.1790	0.0037	Reject H0	Significant
Instructional Applicability	5.2476	0.0081	Reject H0	Significant

This table displays the results of a statistical analysis comparing the evaluation of respondents regarding the acceptability of the LED TV Trainer across different criteria: Design and Construction, Functionality, Durability, Safety, and Instructional Applicability.

In all criteria, the computed ρ -values are all less than the acceptance level of 0.05, hence, the failure to accept the null hypothesis, indicating that in all cases there is enough evidence to conclude that there are indeed significant differences in how respondents evaluate the LED TV Trainer across all evaluated criteria.

These results suggest that different aspects of the LED TV Trainer—design, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability—impact how respondents perceive its overall acceptability. Further, this statistical analysis underscores that respondents' evaluations of the LED TV Trainer vary significantly across different criteria, highlighting the importance of addressing each criterion effectively to enhance overall acceptability and satisfaction among users and stakeholders.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the LED TV Trainer, designed and developed for the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) subject, is highly effective and suitable for educational use, receiving "Very Acceptable" ratings across all evaluated criteria from TLE teachers, electronics experts, and students. The trainer's design, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability were all rated highly, with particular strengths in its instructional effectiveness and safety features. The findings reveal significant differences in how respondents evaluated the trainer, confirming its strong overall acceptability and its potential to enhance skill development and educational outcomes in electronics.

Based on the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that future research on the LED Television Trainer for electronics students focus on longitudinal studies to evaluate its long-term impact on knowledge retention and practical skills application. Comparative studies should also be conducted to benchmark its effectiveness against other educational tools, incorporating detailed feedback from both students and teachers to identify areas for improvement.

In addition, research should explore the integration of the trainer with existing curricula, assess its accessibility across diverse student groups, and ensure alignment with industry demands to maximize its educational value. For enhanced functionality, the mounted multimeters should be made easily detachable for battery replacement, and exposed terminals and banana plugs should be secured with insulators to prevent electric shock. The inclusion of 6-volt lamp beads or LED backlight strips for testing purposes, alongside the existing 3-volt LED lamp beads, is suggested to broaden the trainer's applicability.

Finally, incorporating indicator lights for fault simulation switches is recommended to improve the trainer's durability and operational effectiveness.

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